

UFMA Fossil Collection

Address: Cidade Universitária Dom Delgado, Avenida dos Portugueses, 1966, Bacanga, CEP: 65.000-000, São Luís - MA, Brazil.

Biology Course Coordinator: Dr. Leonardo Dal'Agnol, phone/whatsapp: +55 98 98451-7780
Paleontologist in charge of the collection: Dr. Manuel Alfredo Medeiros (professor and researcher), phone/whatsapp: +55 98 98128-6670

Material sent for publication in 2026

Article: Medeiros et al. "Baby and juvenile vertebrate fossils in strata of the Alcântara Formation: evidence of a nursery site in the early Cenomanian of northeastern Brazil" (submitted).

List of material:

Specimen	Registration number	Plate
Rostral tooth of sawfish <i>Onchopristis</i> sp. (Sclerorhynchidae)	UFMA 1.40.556	1
Rostral tooth of sawfish <i>Atlanticopristis equatorialis</i> (Sclerorhynchidae)	UFMA 1.40.554	2
Tooth of pterosaur Ornithocheiroid, family indet.	UFMA 1.20.618	3
Osteoderm of Crocodylomorpha, family indet.	UFMA 3.10.142	4
Tooth of Carcharodontosaurinae dinosaur, genus indet.	UFMA 1.20.616	5
Tooth of Carcharodontosaurinae dinosaur, genus indet.	UFMA 1.20.617	6

Plate 1

Plate 2

Plate 3

Plate 4

Plate 5

Plate 6

